

of number of silvershoots to tillers/50 hills at 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). GM incidence also was measured at 50 DT on FARO 27, FARO 29, and ITA212 transplanted 20 Aug, 25 Sep, and 25 Oct.

Early-maturing FARO 27 was more

prone to GM infestation at 30-50 DT and medium-maturing FARO 29 at 40-60 DT (see table). The later the transplanting date, the higher the GM incidence (see figure). But many local farmers avoid early planting because they grow upland crops before rice. □

Effect of planting time on GM incidence. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Host plants for yellow rice borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* and white stem borer (WSB) *S. innotata*

A. Arvind, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Tamil Nadu, India

We measured YSB and WSB survival on two weed species common in ricefields. Individually caged plants of *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* were infested separately with newly emerged first-instar YSB and

WSB larvae.

On *C. rotundus*, both YSB and WSB larvae bored into the stem, fed on the inner contents, and pupated below the soil surface. Survival on *C. rotundus* was 78% for YSB and 53% for WSB.

On *C. dactylon*, the larvae scraped the inflorescence peduncle, fed a little on the inner stem contents, but failed to pupate. It could be that stem borer larvae initially feed on *C. dactylon*, then migrate to a newly transplanted rice crop. □

Walking the rice paddy for pest sampling does not affect yield

G.S. Arida and B.M. Shepard, IRRI

It is necessary to walk the rice paddy to sample insect populations. We measured

the effect on yield of walking in the paddy.

Variety IR64 was transplanted 20 d after seeding at 25 × 25 cm. The field was divided into 24 plots measuring 2 × 5 m each. Four treatments (see table) were replicated six times in a

randomized complete block design.

There was no significant difference in yield. □

Effect on yield of walking through rice paddy. IRRI. 1986.

Walking (no./wk)	Yield (t/ha)
0 ^a	2.5
1	2.5
3	2.5
6	2.4

^aPlots not walked on 14-77 d after transplanting.

Occurrence of a virulent rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotype(?) in Andhra Pradesh, India

J.S. Bentur, T.E. Srinivasan, and M.B. Kalode, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

During the 1986 wet season, GM severely damaged rice crops in northeastern Andhra Pradesh, where large tracts were planted to GM-resistant varieties Phalguna (RPW 6-17) and Surekha (developed from IR8/ Siam 29). These varieties were released in 1977 and 1976.

We assessed damage in cooperation with the extension staff of the Department of Agriculture, Andhra Pradesh.

Damage in Phalguna and Surekha averaged more than 50% silvershoots. Maximum damage approached 96%.

Susceptible varieties were severely damaged — CR1014, 33%; Mahsuri, 57%; RNR17, 78%; Sona, 84%; and Swarna, 88%.

Pest buildup was probably favored by high rainfall (410 mm) late Jun to mid-Aug, and frequent cyclonic storms in Sep and Oct, resulting in cloudy and humid periods. Farmers also were not familiar with control measures because GM had not occurred severely for more than 10 yr. Studies over 10 yr under the AICRIP coordinated entomology program have established 3 distinct biotypes, based on reactions to differential donors Eswarakora and

Siam 29/Leaung 152 and their derivatives. The Andhra Pradesh population represented biotype 1.

Apparently, the resistance in Phalguna and Surekha has broken down in response to a new, more virulent biotype.

Other resistant varieties involving donors other than Siam 29 also were affected by the new population. In small minikit plots, Pothana (an Eswarakora derivative) and IR36 (a Ptb derivative) exhibited 40.6% and 22.2% silvershoots. These preliminary studies point toward a possible "new" biotype of GM. □

Some common predators of rice insect pests

N. Q. Kamal, A.N.M.R. Karim, and S. Alam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

We collected predators from ricefields using sweep nets and took visual counts

Some insect predators of rice insect pests recorded at BRRI farm, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1981-84.

Predator	Intensity
COLEOPTERA	
Anthicidae <i>Formicomus</i> sp.	
Carabidae	
<i>Ophionea ishii ishii</i> Habu	High
<i>Ophionea indica</i> Thunberg	
Staphylinidae	
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i> Curtis	High
Cicindellidae	
<i>Cicindela venosa</i> Kollar	Moderate
<i>C. grammophora</i>	Moderate
HEMIPTERA	
Miridae	
<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> sp.	Moderate
<i>Tythus</i> sp.	Moderate
Nabidae	
<i>Stenonabis</i> nr. <i>tagalida</i> Stal	Low
Gerridae	
<i>Limnogonus</i> sp.	Moderate
Mesoveliidae	
<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i> (Horvath)	Moderate
Veliidae	
<i>Microvelia douglasi atrolineata</i> Bergroth	High
Pentatomidae	
<i>Zincroma coerulea</i> Linnaeus	Moderate
Anthocoridae	
<i>Orius tantillus</i> (De Motschulsky)	Moderate
DIPTERA	
Chloropidae	
<i>Anatrichus pygmaeus</i> Lamb	Moderate

of insect predators of rice insect pests 1981-84 (see table). A. T. Barrion of the Entomology Department, International

Rice Research Institute, R. Madge, CIE, London, and M. S. K. Ghauri, CIE, London, identified the specimens. □

A new brown planthopper (BPH) biotype in Parwanipur, Nepal

G.L. Shrestha, National Rice Improvement Program (NRIP), Parwanipur, Birganj, Nepal; and R.R. Adhikary, Parwanipur Agriculture Station, Parwanipur, Birganj, Nepal

We multiplied the local BPH population on susceptible TN1 during the 1984-85 winter season. The biotype was identified by screening on differential rice varieties in the greenhouse. We repeated the screening twice, with three replications each. Damage was scored on individual seedlings using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Mudgo and IR26 with *Bph 1*

resistance gene (resistant [R] to biotypes 1 and 3) were susceptible to the Parwanipur biotype (see table). ASD7, CR94-13, and IR36 with *bph 2* gene for resistance (R to biotypes 1 and 2 but susceptible to biotype 3) were susceptible. The Parwanipur BPH population is not biotype 1, biotype 2, or biotype 3. Rathu Heenathi (*Bph 3* gene) and Babawee (*bph 4* gene) were resistant to the Parwanipur BPH biotype, as were Ptb 33 and Hondarawala with two genes (*bph 2 + Bph 3*) for resistance.

The Parwanipur BPH population appears to be a new biotype. The gene complex of IR56 and IR58 is not fully understood. □

Comparison of differential varietal reactions to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3, and the Parwanipur BPH biotype. Birganj, Nepal, 1984-85 winter.

Gene for resistance and differential variety	Reaction to local biotypes of BPH			Reaction to Parwanipur biotype
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	
<i>Bph 1</i>				
Mudgo	R	S	R	S
IR26	R	S	R	S
<i>bph 2</i>				
ASD7	R	R	S	S
CR94-13	R	R	S	S
<i>Bph 3</i>				
Rathu Heenathi	R	R	R	R
<i>bph 4</i>				
Babawee	R	R	R	R
<i>bph 2 + Bph 3</i>				
Ptb 33	R	R	R	R
Hondarawala	R	R	R	R
No resistance gene				
TN1	S	S	S	S

Seasonal changes in the stem borer (SB) *Maliarpha separata* populations

M.N. Ukwungwu, Rice Research Programme, National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Badeggi, P.M.B. 8, Bida, Nigeria

We studied seasonal population

fluctuations of *M. separata*, a major pest of rice in Nigeria, Jan-Dec 1982 at Badeggi research farm. Ten hills of susceptible variety FARO 11 were dissected at 10-d intervals from transplanting to harvest to count borers.

Insect population was about four times higher in crops transplanted in the dry season (Nov-May) than in the wet